

Automated Attendance System Using Facial Structure

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Abstract - Automated Attendance System using Facial Structure" presents an innovative approach to attendance management, combining facial biometrics and IoT technology for efficient tracking. The project utilizes a Raspberry Pi system to swiftly and accurately identify students' faces captured by a monitor camera. Traditional attendance methods are often cumbersome and prone to errors like proxy attendance. In contrast, this system relies on facial recognition to maintain an accurate record of student presence. During attendance sessions, the system captures images of attendees and employs advanced face detection and recognition techniques. Recognized students are promptly marked present, with attendance records updated to include time, student name, and registration number. The project's development extensively utilizes deep learning techniques, ensuring robust face recognition capabilities. This system marks a significant advancement in attendance management, offering improved accuracy and convenience in educational settings.

Key Words: Automated, biometrics, management, Raspberry pi, OpenCv.

1. INTRODUCTION

"Automated Attendance System using Facial Structure" represents a significant breakthrough in attendance management, fusing advanced facial biometrics with IoT technology to streamline tracking processes. In this system, the integration of Raspberry Pi facilitates the rapid and precise identification of students' faces, transcending the limitations of traditional attendance methods that are often fraught with errors, such as proxy attendance. By harnessing the capabilities of facial recognition technology, this innovative system ensures the maintenance of meticulous attendance records, thereby enhancing accountability and administrative efficiency within educational institutions.

During attendance sessions, the system seamlessly captures images of attendees, leveraging sophisticated face detection algorithms to accurately identify individuals. Recognized students are promptly logged as present, with detailed timestamps, names, and registration numbers recorded to provide comprehensive attendance data. This approach not only minimizes the administrative burden associated with manual attendance tracking but also mitigates the potential

conventional systems. At the core of this system's functionality lies the utilization of deep learning techniques, which enable the development of robust face recognition capabilities.

Through continuous refinement and optimization, the system achieves unparalleled accuracy and reliability in identifying students based on their facial features. This transformative technology represents a significant advancement in attendance management, offering educational institutions a practical and efficient solution for monitoring student attendance.

By adopting the Automated Attendance System using Facial Structure, educational institutions can embrace a more proactive approach to attendance tracking, facilitating timely interventions and support for students as needed. Furthermore, the implementation of this system promotes a culture of accountability and responsibility among students, fostering a conducive learning environment conducive to academic success.

In conclusion, the Automated Attendance System using Facial Structure marks a groundbreaking innovation in attendance management, leveraging facial biometrics and IoT technology to enhance accuracy, efficiency, and accountability in educational settings. As institutions continue to embrace digital transformation, this system stands poised to revolutionize attendance tracking practices, offering a glimpse into the future of educational administration.

1.1 Objectives

Our primary objective is to help the lecturers/teachers, improve and organize the process of tracking and managing student attendance. Additionally, this:

- To capture and mark attendance of the student.
- To compare real-time face with the registered face datasets with the database.
- To store the updated attendance in the "CSV file".
- To extract (download) the attendance information.

2. Problem statement

for inaccuracies and discrepancies. In educational institutions, the traditional methods of attendance management have long been a source of efficiency and error. These manual systems, such as roll calls or card swiping, not only consume valuable time but are also prone to inaccuracies, leading to discrepancies in attendance records. Although facial recognition technology offers a promising solution to automate attendance management, existing systems primarily rely on image comparison techniques. These systems often struggle with reliability due to various environmental factors, including changes in lighting conditions, facial expressions, and occlusions. Consequently, the effectiveness of such systems in accurately capturing and marking attendance in real-time remains limited.

Therefore, there is a pressing need to develop an automated attendance system that goes beyond traditional facial recognition methods by incorporating facial structure analysis. By analysing the unique features of individuals' facial structures, such a system can provide a more robust and reliable method of attendance tracking. This approach offers the potential to overcome the limitations of existing systems, ensuring greater accuracy and efficiency in marking student attendance.

Furthermore, in addition to addressing the technical challenges associated with facial structure analysis, the proposed system must also prioritize data security and privacy. With increasing concerns over the unauthorized use of facial recognition data and potential privacy breaches, it is imperative to implement robust safeguards to protect sensitive information and ensure compliance with regulatory requirements.

In summary, the problem at hand is twofold: first, to develop an automated attendance system that leverages facial structure analysis to enhance accuracy and reliability in real-time attendance tracking, and second, to address the ethical and privacy concerns associated with the use of facial recognition technology in educational settings. By tackling these challenges, the proposed system aims to revolutionize attendance management practices, offering a secure, efficient, and contactless solution for educational institutions.

3. Proposed System

The proposed system aims to streamline the attendance process in educational settings by leveraging facial recognition technology. Each student's face will be captured and stored in a database for attendance purposes. To ensure accurate detection of facial features, it is essential to capture images in a well-lit environment where seating arrangements and student postures can be recognized.

With our system in place, manual attendance taking by teachers becomes obsolete. With our system in place, manual attendance taking by teachers becomes obsolete. Instead, the system automatically records a video of the classroom, and through advanced image processing and training algorithms, it identifies and recognizes the faces of students. Subsequently, the attendance database is updated in a spreadsheet format for easy access and management.

Key components of our system include a Raspberry Pi computer serving as the processing unit and a webcam for capturing images. The Raspberry Pi's compact size and affordability make it an ideal choice for classroom deployment. Additionally, the webcam provides high-quality image capture essential for accurate facial recognition.

By implementing this system, educational institutions can significantly reduce administrative burdens associated with attendance tracking while ensuring accuracy and efficiency. Moreover, the use of readily available hardware components makes our solution accessible and cost-effective for a wide range of educational settings.

3.1 Methodology

Facial recognition methodology is extensively applied in various projects due to its numerous advantages. To effectively trace and track individuals for attendance purposes, the system necessitates data. This data involves associating each individual's image with a unique ID and name. Upon system activation, the option to capture images is provided, requiring prior input of ID and name details. Over 100 grayscale images are then captured using OpenCV, serving as input for Haar cascade processing. Haar Cascade subsequently processes these images into binary format, encoding them as binary images.

Once input is provided, the system undergoes facial feature detection, and the data is stored for further actions. The dataset is structured accordingly to facilitate facial recognition as needed. The "track images" option is then utilized for detecting and recognizing individuals' faces. Following successful face detection, attendance is marked in a spreadsheet, including corresponding date and time details.

3.2 Algorithm

Fig 1. Algorithm Flow of the designed system

The proposed system operates as follows: Upon activation, the system prompts for input, which includes live images of students, along with their respective names and IDs. Following storage and training, the system becomes operational, allowing for image tracking and attendance report generation.

1. Capture Attendance Image
2. Detect face using Haar cascade
3. Convert the captured image into Grayscale for easy comparison of the image
4. Recognize and compare the detected face with the registered face
5. Mark attendance
6. View attendance records

Post-processing: The system records a short video as input, utilizing image processing and training techniques to recognize faces. Subsequently, the attendance database is updated in a spreadsheet format, following the steps outlined in the above pseudo code.

3.3 Architecture

The project utilizes a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B V1.2 as a remote device, serving as the system's computing unit. This device is powered via a raspberry pi official adapter for power supply. Additionally, it is equipped with a webcam for image capture along with the tft display for UI (user interface) and a memory card for storing Pi

contents.

Fig 2. Depiction of Architecture of the project

4. Project Description

Running the project:

- Raspberry Pi Official Power Supply is given for the proper working of the mini computer.
- Raspberry Pi and TFT display are connected via pins.
- Web Cam is connected through the usb serial port with the raspberry pi.

Dataset Creation in Registration Process.

There are three slots for unique database of individual student

- Name
- Id
- Password

Fig 3-Registration Window (credentials entering)

The image is captured using the webcam that is attached to the raspberry pi .100 images are captured for better accuracy, the images are taken right after the set password is entered a window will appear displaying your face. Once the image is captured the window will automatically close and redirects to the fist home page of the UI.

Fig 4-Capturing images to store in the database

The captured images are than stored to the database a folder will be created for every registration, the folder will be saved using the enter named and id and the captured images.

Fig 5 -Dataset folder is created.

Login and attendance marking

You will be asked to provide the credentials when login

- Student id
- Password

After the correct credentials are entered you will be logged in successfully, and can access your account successfully to take attendance, if the credentials are wrong the UI displays the message “unknown credentials”.

Fig 6- Login in with correct credentials.

After login in you a new window will appear displaying the information of the student and a mark attendance button to mark and take attendance.

Fig 7 -Recognizing face and taking attendance.

After the attendance is taken a notification will appear displaying the message according to the consequences of the action of user.

Fig 8-Message displaying attendance is marked

if the person isn't the same person and the face is not recognized when compared the message will show "attendance not marked."

5.Result

The system met its objectives, providing an efficient, accurate, and user-friendly solution for attendance management. With high accuracy, rapid processing, and positive user feedback, it shows potential for widespread adoption and future enhancements.

The project resulted the following-

- Time saved
- Efficiency
- Real-Time
- Accurate
- Scalability
- Security
- Attendance saved in a CSV file

Name	Student ID	Time
100	100	42:36.6
alok	6	49:19.0
Anvesh	25	55:48.9
77	77	00:25.3
anvesh	234	22:30.9

Fig 9-Attendance is saved in the Csv file.

6.Conclusion

The Automated Attendance System using Facial Recognition presents a robust and efficient solution for modern attendance management challenges. By leveraging advanced image processing and machine learning techniques, the system achieves high accuracy and efficiency, significantly reducing the time required for attendance marking.

Despite these achievements, there are areas for improvement, such as enhancing performance under low-light conditions and ensuring consistent accuracy across diverse environments. Future work will focus on these aspects, along with potential integration with other institutional systems to provide a comprehensive attendance management solution.

In conclusion, the Automated Attendance System has proven to be a valuable tool for educational and organizational settings, offering a practical and scalable approach to attendance management. Its successful

deployment and positive user reception underscore its potential for broader application and further innovation.

7.References

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